

Growth-promoting effect of Sulphur 201c in pigs

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Abstract

In a blind, placebo-controlled trial, a homoeopathic dynamized dilution of *Sulphur* 201c was given orally to pregnant sows every 10 days. No significant difference was detected between the birth weight of litters (39 piglets) of treated sows and control litters (40 piglets). On day 30 statistically significant differences were observed both in the final weight of litters, mean total and daily weight gain.

KEYWORDS: Homoeopathic drugs; Growth promoters.

Introduction

Antibiotics and growth-stimulating ergotropic drugs are routinely added to pig diets, with the higher commercial input signifying a health risk for humans and animals. Risks including hormone accumulation, bacterial resistance to antibiotics and sensitization to these in consumers have been documented.¹

Homoeopathy offers a low-cost alternative leaving no toxic residue. A number of controlled and statistically validated studies²⁻¹⁰ have demonstrated its effectiveness as an alternative preventative and therapeutic approach for the farming industry. Of interest is research with growth promoters for animal production.¹¹⁻¹⁸ In the present trial we studied the effect on pork production of homoeopathic growth promoters given to pregnant sows, compared with an equivalent control group.

Growth promoters are traditionally given to young pigs during development, but in Italy¹¹ and France^{13, 14} three controlled trials have been done on the treatment of pregnant sows. The results were statistically significant for homoeopathy, with the young pigs showing increased weight gain at one month. We now present a trial with *Sulphur* 201c and a modified posology aimed at improving previous results.

Materials and method

In a blind pilot study at the pig unit of the

Instituto de Investigaciones en Ciencias Veterinarias (IICV) of Baja University, California, Mexico (UABC), five sows on treatment and five controls were followed during pregnancy. Both groups consisted of cross bred para 2 and 3 Ham, York and Duroc sows. The treated group received *Sulphur* 201c (dil-agit) prepared by diluting 10ml *Sulphur* 200c (manufactured by Propulsora de Homeopatía SA) with 1,000ml water and hand-succussing 50 times. The controls received ethanol 94% in a dilution of 10-1,000ml water, also succussed 50 times.

Both groups received oral doses of the solution every 10 days by spraying their food pellets, using aspersion tanks. Pellets were sprayed by supervised workers without knowledge of the code. The groups were fed standard commercial pellets, as sold mixed with antibiotics in growth-promoting dosage.

Litters were weighed by a worker who did not know the code. Piglet weight was recorded at birth and at weaning, with the mean daily gain per group calculated. Statistical analysis of these parameters was by general mixed model analysis of variance, observing the effect of treatment, sex and interaction of these two variables on weight gain. The code was broken only after the final statistical results were obtained.

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows no significant differences in mean birth weight or days of lactation ($p >$

	Sulphur 201c n = 39	Control n = 40	P
Lactation period	27.5	28.4	> 0.05
Mean birth weight (kg)	2.0	1.8	> 0.05
Mean final weight (kg)	9.4	8.2	< 0.05
Mean weight gain (kg)	7.4	6.4	< 0.05
Mean daily wt gain (kg)	0.269	0.223	< 0.01

TABLE 1. Sulphur 201c as growth-promoting agent in pigs. Final results.

0.05). A statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed in mean, final and daily weight gain ($p < 0.01$).

The fact that piglets were born with similar weight indicates that with treatment actually given during pregnancy the effect on weight is manifest after parturition.

The results show that mean daily weight gain might be the most important parameter, because it controls the influence that differing lactation periods for individual piglets might have on total weight gain.

Sex or sex group interaction variables were found to have no effect on birth weight, final weight, total and daily weight gain ($p > 0.05$). This suggests the observed results were due exclusively to the treatment factor.

Another variable which might influence the dependent variables is the number of parturitions of each sow. This possible effect was controlled from the beginning by including the same number of 2 and 3 para sows in both groups and randomly assigning them to each group.

The results of the present and previous trials prove that dynamized high dilutions given during pregnancy offer new research potential with growth-promoting pharmaceuticals. The litters were not given further doses of the substance, which speaks in favour of economical use and avoids time-consuming manipulations.

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